

Use of YouTube among Social Science Research Scholars at Jadavpur University

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Abstract: *YouTube has become a vital part of modern life, extending its role beyond entertainment to academic and research purposes. It provides access to a wide range of information and supports scholars across various disciplines. This study investigates the use of YouTube by social science research scholars at Jadavpur University. Data were collected through a survey, using a structured questionnaire administered to a systematically selected sample from eight social science departments. The findings reveal that although YouTube is appreciated for its accessibility and engaging content, researchers primarily use it as a supplementary resource rather than a primary academic tool, due to concerns about the reliability and credibility of its content. Additionally, the platform presents several challenges, such as disruptive advertisements, questionable content quality, algorithm-driven distractions, and information overload.*

Keywords: YouTube, Social Media, Academic Research, Information Source, Social Science Scholars, Jadavpur University, YouTube in Education, Research Tools, Digital Learning, Content Credibility

1 Introduction

In the Web 2.0 era, YouTube has become a key platform for research and education in the social sciences. It offers free access to lectures, tutorials, and conference videos, enabling researchers to learn at their own pace. Interactive features promote global collaboration, while academic channels extend research beyond traditional journals. Its visual content simplifies complex ideas and ensures equitable access, fostering innovation and professional growth.

Social sciences provide critical insights into human behavior, social structures, and cultural dynamics. Using qualitative and quantitative methods, fields like sociology, psychology, and political science address issues such as inequality, governance, and public health. They inform policymaking and

sustainable development by analyzing individual and institutional interactions.

YouTube supports social science research by democratizing academic content and facilitating methodological learning through videos and discussions. Researchers benefit from peer engagement and diverse perspectives, though challenges like misinformation and distractions remain. This study examines YouTube's usage, purpose, satisfaction, and impact among social science scholars at Jadavpur University.

2 Objective

This study has made an endeavour to assess the extent, purpose, satisfaction, and influence of YouTube usage among social science researchers in accessing social science-related information.

3 Methodology

To achieve the objective of the study, the survey method was employed to collect the necessary data. As the study population is large and heterogeneous—comprising research scholars from multiple social science departments at the university—a systematic sampling technique was used. A sample was drawn from eight departments: Economics, Education, Film Studies, History, International Relations, Library & Information Science, Physical Education, and Sociology. The selected sample included forty research scholars, consisting of the five senior-most researchers from each department.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire specifically designed for this purpose. The collected data were then analyzed based on the respondents' inputs and presented through charts and tables, in alignment with the study's objectives.

4 Findings

The analysis of the collected data reveals the following findings.

4.1 Gender-wise Division of the Respondents

The following figure shows the gender-wise division of the respondents.

Figure 1: Gender-wise Division of the Respondents

Figure 1 illustrates the gender-wise distribution of the respondents. Out of a total of 40 respondents, 17 are male and 23 are female. This corresponds to 42.5% male and 57.5% female participants.

4.2 Use of YouTube for Educational Purpose

The following figure shows the usage of YouTube for educational purposes.

Figure 2: Use of YouTube for Educational Purpose (%)

Figure 2 illustrates the use of YouTube for educational purposes among the respondents. Among the total participants, 30% strongly agreed that they use YouTube for educational purposes, while 47.5% agreed with the same. However, 15% of the respondents remained neutral, and 7.5% disagreed. This chart clearly indicates that the majority of respondents utilize YouTube as an educational tool.

4.3 Frequency of Use of YouTube

The following chart shows the frequency of use of YouTube by the researchers.

Figure 3: Frequency of Use of YouTube (%)

Figure 3 represents the frequency of YouTube usage among the researchers. According to the data, 27.5% of respondents use YouTube very often, while 52.5% use it often. The remaining 20% remained neutral regarding their frequency of use. Notably, none of the participants reported using YouTube rarely or never, indicating that YouTube has become an important and widely adopted tool among the respondents.

4.4 Duration of YouTube Usage

The following chart represents time duration of usage of YouTube everyday by the respondents.

Figure 4: Time Duration of Usage of YouTube (%)

Figure 4 provides an overview of the duration of YouTube usage among the respondents. The chart reveals that every participant uses YouTube regularly. Specifically, 5% of respondents spend between 30 minutes to 1 hour per day on the platform, while 27.5% use it for 1 to 2 hours. Around 35% of respondents spend 2 to 3 hours, and 22.5% use it for 3 to 4 hours daily. Additionally, 7.5% spend 4 to 5 hours on YouTube, and only 2.5% use it for more than 5 hours each day. Notably, no respondent reported spending less than 30 minutes on the platform, indicating the widespread popularity and strong acceptance of YouTube among the participants.

4.5 Purpose of Use of YouTube

This chart shows the different purposes of usage of YouTube.

Figure 5: Purpose of Use of YouTube (%)

Figure 5 illustrates the various purposes for which respondents use YouTube, presenting five main categories along with the percentage of responses for each. The purposes identified include, general information, research, writing research papers, teaching/lecture, and entertainment.

For general information, 47.5% of respondents strongly agreed that they use YouTube for this purpose, 32.5% agreed, and 20% remained neutral. Notably, none of the participants disagreed or strongly disagreed with this statement.

Regarding research purposes, 37.5% of respondents strongly agreed, 30% agreed, 22.5% remained neutral, while 7.5% disagreed and 2.5% strongly disagreed.

For writing research papers, 22.5% agreed, 32.5% remained neutral, 30% disagreed, and 15% strongly disagreed. Interestingly, none of the respondents strongly agreed with this use.

In terms of teaching or lecture purposes, 17.5% strongly agreed, 32.5% agreed, 37.5% were neutral, 10% disagreed, and 2.5% strongly disagreed.

For entertainment, the responses were overwhelmingly positive: 60% strongly agreed, 20% agreed, and 20% remained neutral. No respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed with using YouTube for entertainment.

This chart clearly demonstrates that the majority of respondents use YouTube primarily for entertainment purposes, followed by general information, research, and then teaching or lecture purposes.

4.6. Advantages and disadvantages of Using YouTube

Table 1 shows the various advantages of using YouTube, while Table 2 presents the disadvantages of using YouTube.

Table 1: Advantages of Using YouTube

Sl. No.	Advantages	Strongly Agree (%)		Agree (%)		Neutral (%)		Disagree (%)		Strongly Disagree (%)	
		No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)
a.	Resources related to social sciences are easily accessible 24*7	12	30	16	40	7	17.5	5	12.5	0	0
b.	Doesn't require anybody's permission to watch those videos on you tube	14	35	17	42.5	5	12.5	4	10	0	0
c.	These videos help researchers to learn complex social concepts easily through graphics	10	25	18	45	8	20	4	10	0	0
d.	Helps to improve listening skill	11	27.5	17	42.5	9	22.5	3	7.5	0	0
e.	You tube videos provide in-depth knowledge on a topic related to social sc. In a short period of time	4	10	9	22.5	22	55	4	10	1	2.5
f.	Researchers can concentrate better while watching videos rather than reading text in the books and periodicals	19	47.5	13	32.5	6	15	1	2.5	1	2.5

Sl. No.	Advantages	Strongly Agree (%)		Agree (%)		Neutral (%)		Disagree (%)		Strongly Disagree (%)	
g.	You Tube always provide updated information on any topic	6	15	7	17.5	14	35	10	25	3	7.5
h.	Every video related to social sciences Is very reliable	0	0	2	5	7	17.5	16	40	15	37.5
i.	You tube can easily replace the need of books and periodicals	0	0	0	0	6	15	16	40	18	45
j.	Anybody can find related topics on social sciences after few searches because of you tube's algorithm	6	15	13	32.5	18	45	3	7.5	0	0
k.	Availability of internet access cannot be a barrier for using you tube	0	0	2	5	6	15	11	27.5	21	52.5

Table 1 illustrates the various advantages of YouTube as perceived by the respondents, showing the percentage of agreement or disagreement with each listed statement. The responses are categorized into five levels: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. A detailed analysis of the responses is given below.

Accessibility of Resources: For the first advantage—“Resources related to social science are easily accessible 24×7”—30% of respondents strongly agreed and 40% agreed. 17.5% remained neutral, while 12.5% disagreed. Notably, no respondent strongly disagreed.

Permission-Free Access: Regarding the second statement—“YouTube videos do not require permission to watch”—35% strongly agreed, 42.5% agreed, 12.5% were neutral, and 10% disagreed. Again, no one strongly disagreed.

Understanding Complex Concepts: For the third advantage—“These videos help researchers learn complex social concepts easily through graphics”—25% strongly agreed and 45% agreed. 20% stayed neutral, while 10% disagreed. No respondents strongly disagreed.

Improving Listening Skills: In response to the statement—“YouTube helps improve listening skills”—27.5% strongly agreed and 42.5% agreed. 22.5% remained neutral and 7.5% disagreed, with no strong disagreement reported.

In-Depth Knowledge in Short Time: For the fifth advantage—“YouTube videos provide in-depth knowledge on social science topics in a short time”—only 10% strongly agreed and 22.5% agreed. A significant 55% remained neutral, 10% disagreed, and 2.5% strongly disagreed.

Better Concentration with Videos: The sixth advantage—“Researchers concentrate better while watching videos than reading texts”—received 47.5% strongly agree and 32.5% agree responses. 15% were neutral, while 2.5% disagreed and another 2.5% strongly disagreed.

Updated Information: On the seventh point—“YouTube always provides updated information on any topic”—15% strongly agreed and 17.5% agreed. However, 35% were neutral, 25% disagreed, and 7.5% strongly disagreed, indicating some skepticism regarding content currency.

Reliability of Content: For the eighth statement—“Every video related to social sciences is very reliable”—none strongly agreed. Only 5% agreed and 17.5% remained neutral, whereas 40% disagreed and 37.5% strongly disagreed. This clearly shows that while YouTube is a useful tool, researchers question the reliability of its content.

Replacing Books and Periodicals: The ninth advantage—“YouTube can replace the need for books and periodicals”—received no agreement. Instead, 40% strongly disagreed and 45% disagreed, while 15% remained neutral. This underscores the continued importance of traditional academic resources.

Search Efficiency: Regarding the statement—“Related topics in social sciences can be found easily due to YouTube’s algorithm”—15% strongly agreed, 32.5% agreed, 45% remained neutral, and 7.5% disagreed. No strong disagreement was recorded.

Internet Access as a Barrier: The final advantage—“Internet access is not a barrier to using YouTube”—was met with skepticism. Only 5% agreed, 15% were neutral, while 27.5% disagreed and 52.5% strongly disagreed. This suggests that internet availability remains a significant limitation for some researchers.

This data suggests YouTube is valued for convenience and engagement but is not seen as a standalone academic resource due to credibility and access issues.

Table: 2 shows various disadvantages of using YouTube.

Table 2: Disadvantages of Using YouTube

Sl. No.	Disadvantages	Strongly Agree (%)		Agree (%)		Neutral (%)		Disagree (%)		Strongly Disagree (%)	
		No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)
a.	In case of YouTube videos, there is a very little space to fill up with your imagination.	0	0	26	65	11	27.5	3	7.5	0	0
b.	Watching YouTube videos related to social sciences. Is not that satisfactory regarding learning new concepts	0	0	0	0	9	22.5	31	77.5	0	0
c.	YouTube shows so many advertisements at the time of learning something important or in the middle of some complex concepts and this always breaks the concentration of researchers.	14	35	19	47.5	7	17.5	0	0	0	0
d.	Every video on YouTube related to social Sc. Doesn't come from a reliable sources	12	30	21	52.5	7	17.5	0	0	0	0
e.	It's tough to concentrate on a single topic due to it's algorithm because related topics tend to appear continuously.	2	5	13	32.5	23	57.5	2	5	0	0
f.	It could be a medium of exposure to inappropriate content for researchers.	9	22.5	28	70	3	7.5	0	0	0	0
g.	Finding relevant information on YouTube is difficult	0	0	6	15	11	27.5	20	50	3	7.5
h.	Information overload	3	7.5	27	67.5	10	25	0	0	0	0
i.	Difficulty in searching	0	0	3	7.5	14	35	23	57.5	0	0
j.	Information can be lost easily	2	5	16	40	18	45	4	10	0	0
k.	YouTube can never replace Printed books and periodicals.	31	77.5	9	22.5	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2 illustrates the various advantages of YouTube as perceived by the respondents, showing the percentage of agreement or disagreement with each listed statement. The responses are categorized into five levels: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. A detailed analysis of the responses is given below.

Limited Imaginative Engagement: Regarding the statement “YouTube videos offer very little room for imagination,” 65% of respondents agreed, while 27.5% remained neutral, and 7.5% disagreed. No respondents strongly agreed or strongly disagreed.

Learning Satisfaction: For the statement “Watching YouTube videos related to social sciences is not satisfactory for learning new concepts,” 77.5% disagreed, and 22.5% were neutral. No respondents expressed agreement or strong disagreement, suggesting that most find YouTube satisfactory for conceptual learning despite its limitations.

Advertisement Interruptions: A significant concern was highlighted in response to the statement “YouTube shows too many advertisements during important learning moments, disrupting concentration.” Here, 35% strongly agreed and 47.5% agreed, while 17.5% remained neutral. No disagreement was reported.

Reliability of Content: On the issue of credibility—“Not every YouTube video on social science comes from a reliable source”—30% strongly agreed and 52.5% agreed, with 17.5% remaining neutral. Again, no disagreement was observed.

Distractions from Algorithm: In response to the statement “It is difficult to concentrate on a single topic due to YouTube’s algorithm suggesting continuous related videos,” 5% strongly agreed and 32.5% agreed. A majority (57.5%) remained neutral, while 5% disagreed. No strong disagreement was recorded.

Limited Imaginative Engagement: Regarding the statement “YouTube videos offer very little room for imagination,” 65% of respondents agreed, while 27.5% remained neutral, and 7.5% disagreed. No respondents strongly agreed or strongly disagreed.

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Distractions from Algorithm: In response to the statement “It is difficult to concentrate on a single topic due to YouTube’s algorithm suggesting continuous related videos,” 5% strongly agreed and 32.5% agreed. A majority (57.5%) remained neutral, while 5% disagreed. No strong disagreement was recorded.

Exposure to Inappropriate Content: A significant 92.5% (22.5% strongly agreed, 70% agreed) felt that YouTube could expose researchers to inappropriate content. Only 7.5% remained neutral; none disagreed.

Difficulty in Finding Relevant Content: On the statement “Finding relevant information on YouTube is difficult,” 15% agreed, 27.5% were neutral, 50% disagreed, and 7.5% strongly disagreed. This mixed response suggests inconsistent user experiences.

Information Overload: Concerning the statement “Information overload,” 7.5% strongly agreed and 67.5% agreed, while 25% were neutral. No respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed, highlighting the overwhelming nature of content on the platform.

Search Difficulties: In response to “Difficulty in searching,” 7.5% agreed, 35% remained neutral, and 57.5% disagreed. No strong agreement or strong disagreement was recorded.

Loss of Information: For the statement “Information can be lost easily,” 5% strongly agreed, 40% agreed, 45% remained neutral, and 10% disagreed. No one strongly disagreed, suggesting moderate concern over content permanence.

Cannot Replace Traditional Resources: A unanimous response was recorded for the statement “YouTube can never replace printed books and periodicals.” Here, 77.5% strongly agreed and 22.5% agreed, while no respondent disagreed, strongly disagreed, or remained neutral. This result clearly reaffirms the continued importance of traditional academic materials.

YouTube’s disadvantages—**unreliable content, ad intrusions, algorithmic distractions, and information overload**—position it as a supplemental, not primary, research tool. While valued for accessibility and engagement, its flaws necessitate cautious use alongside peer-reviewed and printed materials. The unanimous preference for books underscores YouTube’s role as a **convenient but non-authoritative** resource in academia.

4.6 Technique of Searching

The following chart represents different searching techniques used by the social science researchers.

Figure 6: Technique of Searching

Figure 6 illustrates the various techniques employed by respondents to search for information on YouTube. The chart presents four distinct search approaches along with the percentage distribution of usage for each. The techniques include: Keyword Search, Phrase Search, Browsing Recommended Videos While Watching Related Content, and Accessing Content from YouTube Channels Dedicated to Social Sciences.

The data analysis reveals that a majority—67.5%—of researchers most frequently use the keyword search method to find their required information, while 27.5% use it frequently, and 5% use it occasionally. Notably, none of the respondents reported using this method rarely or never.

Similarly, 62.5% of researchers most frequently use the phrase search method, with 30% using it frequently and 7.5% using it occasionally. Again, no respondents reported using this method rarely or never.

In contrast, only 17.5% of researchers most frequently rely on the third method—recommendations while watching related videos. 22.5% use this method frequently, 40% use it occasionally, 17.5% use it rarely, and 2.5% never use it.

The fourth method—searching through YouTube channels focused on social sciences—is most frequently used by just 15% of respondents. 20% use it frequently, 42.5% occasionally, 12.5% rarely, and 10% never use this approach.

These findings clearly indicate that the majority of researchers rely heavily on keyword search (67.5%) and phrase search (62.5%) as their primary methods for finding information on YouTube. In contrast, passive methods like recommended videos and dedicated channels are used less frequently, with higher occasional/rare usage.

This suggests that active, direct search strategies dominate over algorithmic recommendations or curated content for academic purposes.

4.7 Level of Satisfaction

This chart shows the level of satisfaction of the respondents.

Figure 7: Level of Satisfaction (%)

Majority Satisfaction: Over half of the respondents (57.5%) find YouTube effective for their information needs.

Partial Satisfaction: A significant portion (32.5%) feels YouTube meets their needs only partially, suggesting room for improvement in content relevance or depth.

Dissatisfaction: A small but notable group (10%) reports dissatisfaction, indicating that YouTube may not always fulfil specialized academic or research-based queries.

5 Conclusion

The findings of the study reveal that YouTube serves as a useful resource for social science researchers. While it is appreciated for its accessibility and interactive content—and most researchers use it as a supplementary aid—it is not considered a primary academic source due to concerns about reliability and accessibility. Despite its advantages, the platform has several limitations, including intrusive advertisements, questionable content accuracy, algorithm-driven distractions, and information overload.

Researchers continue to prioritize traditional academic materials, viewing YouTube as a complementary tool rather than a replacement. Although most users find it helpful, a small portion express partial or complete dissatisfaction, suggesting that alternative platforms or improved search methods may be needed to meet specific research needs. YouTube remains a valuable, though imperfect, resource that requires critical evaluation for academic use.

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